

NFDI Pilot Node

(Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur - National Research Data Infrastructure)

Data as a common good for excellent research

FACTSHEET FOR: Decision Makers; Scientists; Service Providers

Pilot Node Profile

The NFDI node is operated by the German National Research Data Infrastructure and its 27 consortia.

The main audience are German scientists and their collaboration partners to care for data as a common good.

Pilot Core Services

- **AAI for login and VO management**
{production}
- **Service catalogue as a central endpoint**
{beta}
- **Helpdesk**
{in preparation}
- **Monitoring**
{in preparation}

EOSC Beyond Core Innovation Sandbox

A pre-production environment where a large range of users, from researchers to node operators, can test the latest developments of the EOSC core.

It acts as a Federator Node offering Core Federating Capabilities for the Pilot Nodes.

Pilot Exchange Services

- **public-data.desy.de**
Metadata catalogue with DOI minting capabilities for data publications (catalogue, doi, pid)
- **public-doi.desy.de**
DOI landingpage (doi, pid)
- **sisyphos.desy.de**
Metadata ingestion for the public-data portal (meta-data)
- **sisyphos.desy.de**
Metadata ingestion for the public-data portal (meta-data)
- **hub.nfdi-jupyter.de**
Jupyter4NFDI, a JupyterHub instance (compute, workflow)

User story at-a-glance

Alex Synapse, scientist, is demonstrating how they find services to use with his team for their scientific work.

They first discover the node's User Space and find a dataset with a DOI in the public-data portal after which they deploy a compute infrastructure via EGI's infrastructure manager.

A JupyterHub is then started in the federated cloud and the data from the catalogue is copied and analysed there.

NFDI Node integrations with the Core Innovation Sandbox and other Pilot Nodes

Integrated Core Federating Capabilities from the Core Innovation Sandbox

- AAI
- User Space

Integrated services from other Pilot Nodes

- EGI Infrastructure Manager

Value of the Node piloting activities

The NFDI pilot node will offer transparent access to NFDI and EOSC data management resources for scientists. Transparent guidance through the multitude of services and resources offered by the more than 300 German scientific institutions through the node will be its aim. Ease of access to research products is what the node strives for.

Next steps

Planned development / improvements or scaling actions:

stronger integration with the discovery hub, knowledge graph and User Space are planned in order to add further interoperable resources to the node's capabilities.

About EOSC Beyond

www.eosc-beyond.eu

The ambition of EOSC Beyond is to support the growth of the EOSC in terms of integrated providers and active users by providing new Core technical solutions that allow developers of scientific application environments to easily compose a diverse portfolio of EOSC Resources, offering them as integrated capabilities to researchers.

Useful Links

NFDI Pilot Node:

<https://www.eosc-beyond.eu/pilot/nfdi>

<http://nfdi.de>

<http://nfdi-pilot.desy.de>

<http://public-data.desy.de>

<http://public-doi.desy.de>

<http://sisyphos.desy.de>

<http://hub.nfdi-jupyter.de>

